

Heterogeneous Impact of Health Insurance Enrolment on Medical Spending for the Elderly in China

Authors: *Yuxi Wang and Shaonan Kong*

ABSTRACT

Objectives: Healthcare provision has always been a contentious issue for the Chinese central government, given the ageing yet vast population, underdeveloped medical infrastructure and scarce capable human resources both in hospitals and in smaller institutions such as rehab centres. This paper seeks to identify the effects of insurance enrolment types on health expenditure as well as the probability of incurring high out-of-pocket expense among the elderly in China. The motivation is to assess first of all the progress of the stated direction in terms of insurance coverage, and whether the means or medical schemes, can serve the ultimate goal of improving quality of care and alleviate the economic burden for Chinese elderly.

Methods: The paper used panel data from 2005, 2008, 2011 and 2014 waves of the Chinese Longitudinal Healthy Longevity Survey to investigate how different insurance types can affect both overall medical spending and out-of-pocket expenses. Given that selection into an insurance scheme may be non-random and endogenous, we use an instrumental variable approach with panel fixed effects and random effects.

Preliminary Results: The result shows that enrolling in the public insurance schemes can raise the overall medical expenditure for elderly, and among the various schemes, only the public basic insurance can effectively reduce the likelihood of incurring primarily out-of-pocket expense.

Discussion: On a policy note, the result does not indicate that the different types of insurance schemes should be once again reformed, but rather that they are satisfactory in the very first stage of trying to achieve universal coverage. Such effect is likely due to the opening of new access to health care services that were previously not available for many rural or poor elderly.